

COLLABORATION TO ENHANCE STUDENTS' MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE

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Collaboration to Enhance Students' Mathematics Performance

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Abstract

This research assessed the relationship between students' perception and engagement of the collaborative learning approach in relation to the academic performance in Mathematics of Grade 7 students in Aloguinsan National High School in the Division of Cebu Province for the school year 2023 – 2024. It also utilized a descriptive correlational method, and respondents were identified using simple random sampling in which a member of population had an equal chance of being selected. One hundred forty-six respondents were asked to answer the survey questionnaire in order to measure their level of perception and engagement in the collaborative learning approach. Their academic performance was assessed using their Grade Point Average (GPA) in Mathematics during the 1st quarter of the school year 2023-2024. The data gathered were statistically treated using frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, and Pearson's *r*. Results showed that most of the respondents were females, and their ages were 12 years old. Under the respondent's parent's highest educational attainment, most of them had completed high school and had a combined monthly family income of 10,000 pesos below. In addition, it revealed that there was a high level of student perception towards utilizing a collaborative learning approach in Mathematics. Also, there was a very high level of affective, behavioral, and cognitive engagement, while the level of respondents' academic performance belongs to the proficient group. Moreover, it was also found that there was no significant relationship between students' perception of cooperative learning and their academic performance in mathematics, but there was a significant relationship between the overall data on respondents' engagement and their academic performance in Mathematics. Furthermore, it was concluded that students with positive perceptions of collaborative learning in school might not be directly impact to their grades, but their attitudes of engagement were significantly relevant to their academic performance in mathematics. Hence, a math performance enhancement plan is highly recommended for adoption.

Keywords: *collaborative learning approach, perception, engagement, mathematics academic performance*

Introduction

Mathematics is not simply a school subject but it is a fundamental subject that forms the foundation for many other fields by empowering people to navigate complexities and contributing to societal progress, which is a source of great innovation and logical solutions. It is not only a powerful tool that shaped the minds of individuals and how things work, but it plays a vital role in daily life that is simply influenced by people's actions and decisions through numerous practical applications such as financial management, time management, improved health-care, technological innovation and etc.

Despite all of these, many learners struggle with math, perceiving it as challenging and considered as a complicated subject that often leads to negative attitudes and reluctance to engage in learning, which may have serious consequences for academic success and future opportunities for the learners. There are various reasons why learners may find mathematics difficult, and these include lack of confidence, lack of foundational skills, poor teaching, limited opportunities for practice, lack of interest, lack of parental support, and lack of real-world applications. To address these challenges faced by the learners and make mathematics more interesting, there was a growing movement towards a paradigm shift in the teaching of math education in which the teachers in public schools should make mathematics concepts relatable and fun for the learners. Several things could be done to help students who struggle with mathematics by providing support and improving their understanding, such as utilizing games and hands-on activities, providing individualized instructions and explorations, building confidence, and creating a positive learning environment. It is important to remember that learning Mathematics is a journey, not a destination because it is a skill that can be learned with time and effort in order for all learners to succeed in the subject. However, it can't be denied that students' mathematics performance continued to be a major concern in the Philippine education system due to negative attitudes and anxiety, socio-economic disparities, ineffective teaching methods, cultural influences, and lack of adequate resources and support. This issue is particularly true in the case of Philippine basic education, as reflected in the overall performance of secondary students.

Apparently, the Philippine performance in the Trends of International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) in 2019 was one of the country's criteria for measuring students' achievement. Based on the recent ranking, it has consistently below the average of participating countries. The Philippines ranked 38th out of 58 countries in Grade 8 mathematics with an average score of 395 and Grade 8 science ranked 40th out of 58 countries with an average score of 383, which is both significantly lower than the average score of 500 (TIMSS 2019 International Results in Mathematics and Science, Mullis et al., 2019). Moreover, studying the issue of students' performance has extended beyond simple to complex issues of intelligence, and it is also considered the center of interest in the educational sector. Similarly, it has been observed that students' mathematics performance at the Grade 7 level of Aloguinsan National High School was one of the concerns of complex issues with a multitude of contributing factors, which was a significant challenge in education that requires attention and targeted solutions. Hence, there is need to assess the students' perception of collaborative learning

and the extent to which they are engaged so the learners can prepare better for entering eighth grade with a stronger foundational understanding of abstract math concepts tested by TIMSS. Practicing and ensuring the essential steps of effective learning styles could help all learners reach their full potential. It could also strengthen their critical thinking skills to perform better on the assessment and strengthen their grasp of advanced mathematical concepts to ensure a smoother transition in the curriculum. The TIMSS results provide continuous documentation of the students need to put greater emphasis on improving the teaching and learning of Mathematics in the country.

Furthermore, it is essential to continue to invest in Mathematics and Science Education in the Philippines, which are essential for preparing students for success in the 21st century. Teaching strategies are also one of the factors that could affect students' mathematics performance and cater to different learning styles, which could make a world of difference. It isn't just about acquiring knowledge but also cultivates a love of learning and fosters a collaborative spirit where students are kept from being bored and feel empowered to learn and grow together. At the same time, the collaborative learning approach is one of the best teaching strategies that could help learners to boost their confidence and feel comfortable by sharing their ideas, which have been observed to manifest interest in learning the subject and encourage learners to be more engaged. Moreover, implementing collaborative learning strategies could effectively enhance students' engagement and improve their overall academic performance in mathematics. However, it is essential to acknowledge that some learners may still struggle with the subject matter even if collaborative learning strategies are employed. This is likely due to a combination of factors, including individual learning styles, prior knowledge gaps, unstructured groups, personality, and confidence.

The most important reason for conducting this study lies in its potential to revolutionize how mathematics is learned and understood within the school. This study delves into the power of collaborative learning, aimed to unlock a more engaging and effective approach to mathematics education that ultimately improves students' academic performance. It further examined the relationship between students' perceptions and engagement in collaborative learning towards their academic performance in mathematics. The output of this study is to present the math performance enhancement plan materials by integrating a collaborative learning approach.

Thus, this study would benefit students, teachers, stakeholders, and curriculum planners who would examine and evaluate students' unique learning styles and integrate the various resources that fall under the educational sector's umbrella to make learning more effective for 21st-century learners.

Research Questions

This research assessed the students' perception and engagement of the collaborative learning approach in relation to the academic performance in Mathematics of the Grade 7 students in Aloguinsan National High School in the Division of Cebu Province for the school year 2023-2024 as the basis for math performance enhancement plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.2. parents' highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.3. combined family monthly income?
2. What is the level of perception of the respondents towards utilizing collaborative approach in learning Mathematics?
3. What is the level of engagement of the respondents in learning Mathematics in terms of:
 - 3.1. affective engagement;
 - 3.2. behavioral engagement; and
 - 3.3. cognitive engagement?
4. What is the level of academic performance of the respondents in mathematics?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the:
 - 5.1. respondents' perception towards collaborative learning and their academic performance in mathematics; and
 - 5.2. respondents' engagement and their academic performance in Mathematics?
6. Based on the findings, what math performance enhancement plan may be crafted?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive-correlational design in which the researcher primarily describes relationships among variables without seeking a causal connection (Mustieles 2020). The design of this study aimed to assess the perception and engagement of the Grade 7 students in collaborative learning towards their academic performance in Mathematics using the data gathered from the survey questionnaire. The participants of the study would be the Grade 7 students of Aloguinsan National High School (ANHS) for the school year 2023 –2024. Respondents were identified using simple random sampling, in which the sampling method of each member of a population had an equal chance of being selected. The data gathered were organized, summarized, and statistically treated in accordance with the objectives of the study.

Respondents

This study focused on the Grade 7 students who are enrolled in Aloguinsan National High School during the academic year of 2023 – 2024. There were 292 respondents of the Grade 7 level who take the mathematics subject. Due to a large population group, the researcher used 50 percent of the total student population, and there were 146 respondents randomly selected to answer the survey questionnaires from different sections. In addition, examining their level of perception and level of engagement in collaborative learning provided significant information that would help the stakeholders to understand the status of the students in this school. Moreover, their academic performance in mathematics was also measured by how they participated in the collaborative learning activities during math sessions. The distribution of the respondents is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

<i>Grade & Section</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Grade 7 - Special Program in Science	38	19	13.01
Grade 7 - Earth	42	21	14.38
Grade 7 - Jupiter	44	22	15.07
Grade 7 - Saturn	42	21	14.38
Grade 7 – Mars	44	22	15.07
Grade 7 – Neptune	40	20	13.70
Grade 7 - Mercury	42	21	14.38
Total	292	146	100.00

Instrument

The researcher utilized a survey questionnaire to gather information that helped to achieve the study's aims. The survey questionnaire consists of the following:

Part I. Profile of the Respondents

This part contains the demographic profile with the respondents' background pertaining to their age, gender, parents' educational attainment, and combined family income.

Part II. Perception of Students Questionnaire by Ingleton (2000)

The second part of the questionnaire was the adapted instrument on student perceptions towards collaborative learning strategy measured by Ingleton (2000). The instrument of this study has 18 indicators rated by the respondents using a five-point Likert scale: 5 strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neither agree nor disagree, 2 disagree and 1 Strongly disagree to make the participants understand the questions easier.

Part III. Student Engagement Survey Questionnaire by Hart et al. (2011)

The third part was an adapted instrument from the Student Engagement in Schools Questionnaire (SESQ) by Hart et al. (2011). The questionnaire items address the aspects of affective, behavioral, and cognitive engagement, which are rated by the respondents using a five-point Likert scale, namely: 5 strongly agree, 4 agree, 3 neither agree nor disagree, 2 disagree and 1 Strongly disagree, which focused on the comprehensive assessment of the construct of student engagement. In addition, the content validity will be examined by the two mathematics teachers not otherwise involved in the study and one university professor who specializes in mathematics education to check for correctness and consistency. Moreover, the researcher also asked for the adviser's assistance to retrieve their grades, particularly in mathematics.

Procedure

Preliminary Stage. The researcher sent a transmittal letter to the principal's office of the Aloguinsan National High School, asking permission to conduct the study. Upon the receipt of the approval of the principal, an ocular visit was conducted to identify the focal person when administering the questionnaires executed and agreed with the concerned person on the date of the orientation and data gathering.

Data Gathering Stage. On the scheduled day, the researcher would facilitate an orientation regarding the research. Salient issues like the purpose of the study, its procedure, and how the confidentiality of the respondents was protected and discussed. Administration of the survey questionnaires followed right after the orientation. Instructions were given on how to answer the survey questionnaires. Assistance was also provided while the respondents answered the survey questionnaires and enough time was given to answer the said questionnaires. Retrieval of the questionnaires followed.

Post Data Gathering Stage. The researchers will tally, organize, summarize, interpret, and analyze the results. Appropriate statistical tools would be used in the treatment of data. An enhancement plan will be proposed to address the needs of the Grade 7 students studying at Aloguinsan National High School.

Data Analysis

After data collection, the data gathered underwent different statistical treatments with the aid of the statistician. To arrive at reliable results, the following statistical tools were used:

Frequency Count. This tool was used to determine the number of characteristics in which the respondents fell in the same category, particularly in the profile.

Percentage. This tool will be utilized to describe the proportion of the respondents who belonged to the same category in relation to the total number of respondents specifically on their profile.

Weighted Mean. This statistic will be used to numerically describe perception, student engagement, performance, and interpretation based on the descriptive rating.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). This statistical tool will determine the strength of the correlation between students' perception, student engagement, and performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the analysis and in-depth interpretations of the data gathered in this study, such as respondents' profiles, level of their perception towards utilizing the collaborative learning approach, level of their engagement, and level of their academic performance in mathematics. Furthermore, the significance of the relationship between the respondent's perception of collaborative learning, attitudes toward their engagement, and their academic performance in mathematics was also tested. Hence, the narrative discussions are given before each table, and a more comprehensive discussion follows each table.

With the help of the responses to the survey questionnaire, the following results and findings were hereby analyzed and presented. Also, the following parts of empirical data of these findings are considered and discussed as follows:

Profile of the Respondents

This section outlined the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, parents' highest educational attainment, and combined family monthly income, which is crucial for interpreting. The researcher aimed to gain valuable insight into a diverse perspective that contributed to the research findings.

Age and Gender

Table 2. Age and Gender of the Respondents

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
14 and above	1	0.68	3	2.05	4	2.74
13	22	15.07	25	17.12	47	32.19
12	51	34.93	42	28.77	93	63.70
11	2	1.37	0	0.00	2	1.37
Total	76	52.05	70	47.95	146	100.00

As shown in Table 2, there were 76 out of 146 respondents were female students, which comprised 52.05 percent of the respondent's total population, while 70 or 47.95 percent were male students. It also revealed in the table that fifty-one or 34.93 percent of the female students whose age were 12 years old while forty-two or 28.77 percent were male followed by Twenty-two or 15.07 percent female whose age were 13 years old while twenty-five or 17.12 percent were male, and another two or 1.37 percent female whose age were 11 years old only in the female side. Moreover, there were one or 0.68 percent of female whose age were 14 years old and above, while 3, or 2.05 percent, were male. In this context, the respondents' ages range from 11 to 14 years old and above. This implies that the Grade 7 learners are typically between 12 and 13 years old which undergo significant cognitive and emotional growth. Also, most of them had entered school on the proper age requirement by DepEd which going through similar developmental stages where the classrooms become a symphony of learning. This allows teachers to tailor their teaching methods to a more consistent level of maturity. Moreover, lessons can be appropriately challenging while also providing the necessary support for students to grasp new concepts.

According to Aransi (2018), teaching strategies at the high school level should take into account of the age and gender diversity among students. From this perspective, learning about diverse cultures in school helps students feel more at ease and secure with these differences. This creates a dynamic learning environment where the learners can learn from each other. As a result, students can socialize with various social groupings and paves the way for a more positive and successful learning experience. In fact, there is no age and gender discrimination in entering High School and gives equal educational opportunity that presents inclusive education to all the learners.

Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Parents' highest educational attainment is linked to socio-economic status and provides a foundation in supporting children's academic

success. Also, it was considered an important variable that needs to be determined in this study and could help interpret the results. Data gathered were presented in table 3 below.

Table 3. *Parents' Highest Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Mother</i>		<i>Father</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Doctorate Graduate	0	0.00	1	0.68
With Doctorate Units	1	0.68	0	0.00
Master's Graduate	2	1.37	1	0.68
With Master's Units	2	1.37	3	2.05
College Graduate	12	8.22	16	10.96
College Level	12	8.22	12	8.22
High School Graduate	49	33.56	33	22.60
High School Level	27	18.49	35	23.97
Elementary Graduate	20	13.70	14	9.59
Elementary Level	21	14.38	30	20.55
No Formal Schooling	0	0.00	1	0.68
Total	146	100.00	146	100.00

Table 3 shows that the respondents on the mother side have 0.68 percent who attained a doctorate, and 1.37 percent successfully finished their master's degree. Another 1.37 percent earned master's units, followed by 8.22 percent who successfully finished their college degree. Also, 8.22 percent achieving their college level, and 33.56 percent completed high school. It also revealed that 18.49 percent reached the high school level, followed by 13.70 percent who completed their elementary and 41.38 percent who attained the elementary level. On the other hand, among the father respondents, 0.68 percent have successfully finished their doctorate and master's degree. Another 2.05 percent earned master's units, and 10.96 percent who successfully finished their college degree, followed by 8.22 percent achieving their college level. In addition, 22.60 percent completed high school, and 23.97 percent attained high school. Also, 9.59 percent completed their elementary. Another 20.55 percent attained their elementary level, and 0.68 percent have no formal schooling.

This implies that the highest percentage was 33.56 percent on the mother's side, which shows that most mothers respondents are high school graduates. Having completed High School, mothers can serve as role models who value education. Their educational background equips the foundation to understand the basic concepts and to assist their children in various subject.

In comparison, the highest rate on the father's side was 23.97 percent, which means most of the respondents' fathers have a high school level of their educational attainment. Perhaps, fathers can demonstrate the importance of lifelong learning and perseverance to their children even if their formal education stopped at High School. Although, most of the respondents' parents have enough educational background that have the potential to be a strong advocate and being a good role models for their children's education. Furthermore, the ability to provide both tangible resources and intangible support empowers parents to guide their children during their learning journey. Kean et al. (2020) found that parental educational attainment influenced children's academic performance. Parents can help their children by providing tangible resources and intangible support for a better academic outcome.

Therefore, the parental educational attainment plays a crucial role in shaping students' academic success which has a significant impact that extends beyond individual families in influencing the overall educational landscape of a community.

Combined Family Monthly Income

Total household income is the total cash net income received by the household and all its members in the defined reference period. The distribution of the combined family income is presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. *Combined Family Monthly Income*

<i>Monthly Income (in pesos)</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Above 30,000	1	0.68
25,001-30,000	1	0.68
20,001-25,000	19	13.01
15,001-20,000	13	8.90
10,001-15,000	36	24.66
10,000 and below	76	52.05
Total	146	100.00

As shown in Table 4, out of 146 respondents, 76 or 52.05 percent of their families have an income of 10,000 and below. This is followed by 36 or 24.66 percent of the respondents whose family had an income within the 10,001-15,000 brackets. Another 13 or 8.90 percent of them have a monthly income within the bracket of 15,001-20,000. Also, 19 or 13.01 percent, have a family monthly income within the bracket of 20,001-25,000, and both 1 or 0.68 percent, whose family monthly income is within the 25,001-30,000 and above.

This implies that most of the respondents' family had a very low monthly income that belongs to the poverty line. A family with an

income of P10,000 and below is expected to be struggling with their daily expenses. So that, a large family cannot afford to live decently with a meager income of P 10, 000 monthly (IBON, 2018).

Level of Perception of the Respondents Towards Utilizing Collaborative Approach in Learning Mathematics

This section presents the respondents' perception of utilizing a collaborative approach in learning mathematics based on the different indicators.

Table 5. *Level of Perception of the Respondents towards Utilizing Collaborative Approach in learning Mathematics*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Help me understand the materials.	4.29	Very High
2	Help students to exchange knowledge, information, and experience.	4.16	High
3	Make me solve problem easier.	3.94	High
4	Stimulate critical thinking.	3.64	High
5	Makes me more relax in learning	4.10	High
6	Provides me with helpful feedback.	4.15	High
7	Helps me be responsible for myself and the group.	4.37	Very High
8	Provides me with a better understanding.	4.17	High
9	Improved my communication skills.	4.15	High
10	Improved my performance.	4.36	Very High
11	Makes me actively participate in the learning process.	4.16	High
12	Is fun learning strategy.	4.31	Very High
13	Makes me have more new friends.	4.05	High
14	Increased my team spirit.	3.97	High
15	Waste my time explaining to others.	2.18	Low
16	Is difficult for my friends to actively participate in tasks.	2.68	Moderate
17	Should be encouraged/continued	4.05	High
18	Should have a maximum group size of four people.	3.80	High
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.92	High

Legend: 4.21-5.00-Very High; 3.41-4.20-High; 2.61-3.40-Moderate; 1.81-2.60-Low; 1.00-1.80-Very Low

As presented in the Table 5, the level of respondents' perception was very high in items 1, 7, 10, and 12, indicated by the statements "Help me understand the materials," "Helps me be responsible for myself and the group," "Improved my performance," "and is a fun learning strategy," which a had highest weighted means from 4.29 to 4.37. In addition, in items 2,3,4,5,6,8,9,11,13,14,17 and 18 indicated by the statements "Help students to exchange knowledge, information, and experience," "Make me solve problem easier," "Stimulate critical thinking," "Makes me more relax in learning," Provides me with helpful feedback," "Provides me with a better understanding," "Improved my communication skills," "Makes me actively participate in the learning process," "Makes me have more new friends," "Increased my team spirit," "Should be encouraged/continued," and "Should have a maximum group size of four people," which a had high weighted means from 3.64 to 4.17. Moreover, item 16 has a moderate weighted mean of 2.68, which indicates the statement "Is difficult for my friends to actively participate in tasks," while item 15 has a low weighted mean of 2.18, which indicates the statement "waste my time explaining to others." The respondents generally utilized a high perception towards collaborative approach in learning mathematics. This implies that the learners have a positive perception of collaborative learning can lead to greater participation, effort and excitement about the learning process. Additionally, it can unlock a powerful combination of academic achievement and personal development where the students can feel comfortable and valued. Therefore, Hagan et al. (2020) recommended the implementation of cooperative learning can develop student interest and diminish students' negative perceptions that gives students positive attitude towards assessment, enabling them to enjoy learning with their peers.

Level of the Respondents' Engagement in Learning Mathematics

This section presents respondents engagement in learning mathematics in terms of affective, behavioral and cognitive.

Affective Engagement

This section presents the level of the respondents' engagement in learning mathematics in terms of affective engagement.

Table 6 shows respondents' engagement in learning mathematics in terms of affective engagement, and the level of engagement of the respondents was very high in all items which have a weighted mean from 4.59 to 4.89, indicated by the statements "I am very interested in learning," "I think what we are learning in school is interesting," "I like what I am learning in school," "I enjoy learning new things in class," "I think learning is boring," "I like my school," "I am proud to be at this school," "Most mornings, I look forward to going to school," and "I am happy to be at this school." This implies that the learners have a very high level of emotional response characterized by feelings of involvement such as interest, enjoyment, and a sense of belonging. When learning is enjoyable and associated with positive emotions, learners were likely to develop a love of learning that extends beyond the classroom that requires continuous learning and adaptation.

This emotional engagement unlocks a cascade of benefits that could profoundly impact a learner's success and overall educational experience. (Isohäätä et al., 2019; Järvenoja et al, 2020) stated that socioemotional interactions empower students to see themselves as capable learners within a supportive community. This collaborative spirit fosters intrinsic motivation that propels students beyond mere engagement. It fuels a passion for knowledge that transcends the classroom walls. Therefore, positive emotions act as a catalyst, transforming the "have to" mentality into a genuine "want's to" learn. This shift empowers students to align their personal goals and learning styles, fostering active participation in the learning process.

Table 6. *Level of Engagement of the Respondents in learning Mathematics in terms of Affective Engagement*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I am very interested in learning.	4.79	Very High
2	I think what we are learning in school is interesting.	4.71	Very High
3	I like what I am learning in school.	4.72	Very High
4	I enjoy learning new things in class.	4.71	Very High
5*	I think learning is boring.	4.59	Very High
6	I like my school	4.87	Very High
7	I am proud to be at this school	4.89	Very High
8	Most mornings, I look forward to going to school.	4.64	Very High
9	I am happy to be at this school.	4.84	Very High
Aggregate Weighted Mean		4.74	Very High

Legend: 4.21-5.00-Very High; 3.41-4.20-High; 2.61-3.40-Moderate; 1.81-2.60-Low; 1.00-1.80-Very Low

Behavioral Engagement

This section presents the level of the respondents' engagement in learning mathematics in terms of behavioral engagement.

Table 7. *Level of Engagement of the Respondents in learning Mathematics in terms of Behavioral Engagement*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I try hard to do well in school.	4.24	Very High
2	In class, I work as hard as I can	4.31	Very High
3	When I'm in class, I participate in class activities	4.37	Very High
4	I pay attention in class.	4.78	Very High
5	When I'm in class, I just act like I'm working	3.52	High
6	In school, I do just enough to get by	3.50	High
7	When I'm in class, my mind wanders	3.88	High
8	If I have trouble understanding a problem, I go over it again until I understand it.	3.79	High
9	When I run in to a difficult homework problem, I keep working at it until I think I've solved it.	3.77	High
10	I am an active participant of school activities such as sport day and school picnic	4.25	Very High
11	I volunteer to help with school activities such as sport day and parent day.	4.03	High
12	I take an active role in extracurricular activities in my school.	3.87	High
Aggregate Weighted Mean		4.03	High

Legend: 4.21-5.00-Very High; 3.41-4.20-High; 2.61-3.40-Moderate; 1.81-2.60-Low; 1.00-1.80-Very Low

Table 7 shows respondents' behavioral engagement in learning mathematics. As presented in the table, The level of engagement is very high in items 1,2,3,4 and 10, indicated by the statements "I try hard to do well in school," "In class, I work as hard as I can," "When I'm in class, I participate in class activities," "I pay attention in class" and "I am an active participant of school activities such as sports day and school picnic." which had a highest weighted means from 4.24 to 4.78.

On the other hand, items for 5,6,7,8,9,11 and 12 indicate that the respondents have a high engagement in learning mathematics in the statements "When I'm in class, I just act like I'm working," "In school, I do just enough to get by," "When I'm in class, my mind wanders," "If I have trouble understanding a problem, I go over it again until I understand it." "When I run into a difficult homework problem, I keep working at it until I think I've solved it." "I volunteer to help with school activities such as sports day and parent day," and "I take an active role in extracurricular activities in my school." which had a weighted mean from 3.52 to 4.03. Behavioral engagement implies that students' demonstration, concentration and persistence in learning adopts the different strategies to solve the mathematics problems and embark on a rewarding learning journey. Students who exhibit a high level of behavioral engagement in math are more likely to develop a positive attitude.

In addition, students who felt value towards mathematics provide the incentive to participate behaviorally, which significantly impacts their academic achievement (Gjicali & Lipnevich, 2021; Hwang & Son, 2021; Chen et al., 2018). This type of engagement unlocks a treasure trove of benefits, from a strong foundation in mathematical concepts to the development of critical thinking and problem-

solving skills. This positive reinforcement loop motivates students to continue engaged with mathematics and equips them with valuable tools that can be applied to a wider range of academic disciplines to navigate complexities. Therefore, students who develop these skills are better prepared to thrive in an ever-changing world.

Cognitive Engagement

This section presents the level of the respondents' cognitive engagement in learning mathematics.

Table 8. *Level of Engagement of the Respondents in learning Mathematics in terms of Cognitive Engagement*

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	When I study, I try to understand the material better by relating it to things I already know.	4.13	High
2	When I study, I figure out how the information might be useful in the real world.	4.34	Very High
3	When learning new information, I try to put the ideas in my own words.	4.05	High
4	When I study, I try to connect what I am learning with my own experiences.	4.02	High
5	I make up my own examples to help me understand the important concepts I learn from school.	3.97	High
6	When learning things for school, I try to see how they fit together with other things I already know.	3.92	High
7	When learning things for school, I often try to associate them with what I learnt in other classes about the same or similar things	3.97	High
8	I try to see the similarities and differences between things I am learning for school and things I know already.	4.25	Very High
9	I try to understand how the things I learn in school fit together with each other.	4.27	Very High
10	I try to match what I already know with things I am trying to learn for school.	4.23	Very High
11	I try to think through topics and decide what I'm supposed to learn from them, rather than studying topics by just reading them over.	4.15	High
12	When studying, I try to combine different pieces of information from course material in new ways.	4.38	Very High
Aggregate Weighted Mean		4.14	High

Legend: 4.21-5.00-Very High; 3.41-4.20-High; 2.61-3.40-Moderate; 1.81-2.60-Low; 1.00-1.80-Very Low

Table 8 shows respondents' cognitive engagement in learning mathematics. As presented in the table, The level of engagement is very high in items 2,8,9,10, and 12, indicated by the statements "When I study, I figure out how the information might be useful in the real world," "I try to see the similarities and differences between things I am learning for school and things I know already," "I try to understand how the things I learn in school fit together with each other," "I try to match what I already know with things I am trying to learn for school," "When studying, I try to combine different pieces of information from course material in new ways," which had a highest weighted mean from 4.23 to 4.38. On the other hand, items 1,3,4,5,6,7 and 11 indicate that the respondents have a high engagement in learning mathematics in the statements "When I study, I try to understand the material better by relating it to things I already know," "When learning new information, I try to put the ideas in my own words," "When I study, I try to connect what I am learning with my own experiences," "I make up my own examples to help me understand the important concepts I learn from school," "When learning things for school, I try to see how they fit together with other things I already know," "When learning things for school, I often try to associate them with what I learnt in other classes about the same or similar things," and "I try to think through topics and decide what I'm supposed to learn from them, rather than studying topics by just reading them over," which had a weighted mean from 3.92 to 4.15.

This implies that student cognitive engagement is the expenditure of thoughtful energy needed to comprehend complex ideas in order to go beyond the minimal requirements. Also, the process of attention involved the mental activities for regulation, contemplation, and understanding for complicated ideas related to the learning process. Hence, innovation and problem-solving have the most significant opportunity to emerge from metacognitive thinking processes (Timonen & Ruokamo, 2021). Therefore, cognitive engagement translates better knowledge retention and ability to think innovatively, empowering the learners to be well-rounded.

Summary on the Level of the Respondents' Engagement in Learning Mathematics

This section summarizes the level of the respondent's engagement in learning mathematics, including affective, behavioral and cognitive.

Table 9 shows the summary of the different learning engagements. It shows that affective engagement has a very high level of 4.74,

while behavioral engagement has a high level of 4.03, and cognitive engagement has a high level of 4.14 weighted mean. The summary implies that the learners are very much engaged, committed, and eager to learn the subject. In fact, there is a connection between the three engagement factors in terms of affective, behavioral, and cognitive engagement wherein students' display a level of attention, interest, passion, and positivity while learning. According to (Abubakar et al., 2018), students' engagement is generally considered to be among the best predictors of learning and personal development. Implying this approach can help the learners to develop a positive mathematical identity. (Mazana et al. 2018) discovered that students who engaged in collaborative learning had a more positive attitude towards mathematics and improved their self-efficacy. Therefore, student engagement is the golden key that unlocks the door for their academic success, creating a stronger foundation and better knowledge retention.

Table 9. Summary on the Level of Engagement of the Respondents in learning Mathematics

Components	WM	Verbal Description
Affective Engagement	4.74	Very High
Behavioral Engagement	4.03	High
Cognitive Engagement	4.14	High
Grand Mean	4.30	Very High

Level of Academic Performance of the Respondents In Math

This portion presents the respondents' academic performance for the first quarter of the school year 2023 – 2024. The distribution of their performance is shown in Table 10 below.

Table 10. Level of Academic Performance of the Respondents in Math

Level	Numerical Range	f	%
Advanced	90-100	34	23.29
Proficient	85-89	59	40.41
Approaching Proficiency	80-84	39	26.71
Developing	75-79	14	9.59
Beginning	74 and below	0	0.00
Total		146	100.00
Mean			85.92
St. Dev.			4.53

As shown in Table 10, the majority of respondents had a proficient performance, which composed 59 or 40.41 percent of the 146 respondents with a numeral range of 85-89, followed by 39 or 26.71 percent of the respondents who had approaching proficiency performance with a numerical range of 80-84. On the other hand, 34 or 23.29 percent of them had advanced performance with a numerical range of 90-100, and 14 or 9.59 percent had a developing performance with a numerical range of 75-79. Moreover, the mean average of the performance level is 85.92 with a standard deviation of 4.53. Therefore, the summary shows that the level of respondents' academic performance with a mean of 85.92, belongs to the proficient group.

This implies that most students enrolled in a public institution with a strong GPA's can open doors to a higher education opportunity and maintain good performance to continue to avail the privileges provided by the school. However, students who struggle to adjust to the demands of the school could experience frustrations, which negatively affects their performance. This disruptive behavior can hinder students' learning and isolate them from social and emotional support. By understanding their strength and weaknesses, students can take ownership of their learning journey, fostering a sense of empowerment and drive for continuous improvement to embrace new learning experiences. According to (Hellias et al., 2018), the academic achievement of performance is a cornerstone measured by continuous assessments and the student's overall cumulative grade point average (CGPA). Therefore, continuous assessments offer frequent snapshots of student learning, allowing teachers to identify areas where students excel and build upon the skills or might need additional support and persevere through the difficulties.

Relationship Between the Respondents' Perception Towards Cooperative Learning and Their Academic Performance

Table 11. Test of significant relationship between the respondents' perception towards cooperative learning and their academic performance in Math

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	p-value	Decision	Result
Perception and Academic Performance in Math	0.060	Negligible Positive	0.475	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

*Significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed)

As shown in Table 11, the relationship was tested using Pearson r at 0.05 level of significance with the two-tailed test. The computed value of r is 0.060, a negligible positive correlation between respondents' perception towards cooperative learning and their academic performance. It was further found that the computed p-value of 0.475 is greater than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.475 > 0.05$), which signifies that the null hypothesis is not rejected. This correlation implies that there is not enough evidence to conclude that a positive or negative perception of cooperative learning directly impacts students' mathematics performance. However, (Oden et., al 2021)

reported that students who recognize that their teacher often applies mathematical content to daily life are more interested and showed good performance. Moreover, having a positive level of student's perception towards cooperative learning would increase their performance in school. Hagan et al. (2020) recommended that teachers must sustain students' positive perceptions of mathematics.

Relationship Between the Respondents' Engagement and Their Academic Performance In Math

This section presents the relationship between the respondents' engagement and their academic performance.

Table 9. *Test of significant relationship between the respondents' engagement and their academic performance in Math*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>Strength of Correlation</i>	<i>p - value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Result</i>
Affective Engagement and Academic Performance	0.416*	Weak Positive	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Behavioral Engagement and Academic Performance	0.646*	Moderate Positive	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Cognitive Engagement and Academic Performance	0.674*	Moderate Positive	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant

*Significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed)

As shown in Table 9, the relationship was tested using Pearson r at 0.05 level of significance with the two-tailed test. For affective engagement, the computed value of r which is 0.416 signifies a weak positive correlation between respondents' affective engagement and their academic performance. It was further found that the computed p -value of 0.000 is lesser than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. On the other hand, the computed value of r for behavioral engagement is 0.646, which signifies a moderate positive correlation between respondents' behavioral engagement and their academic performance. It was discovered also that the computed p -value of 0.000, which is lesser than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) then the null hypothesis is rejected. Furthermore, the computed value of r for cognitive engagement is 0.647, which signifies a moderate positive correlation between respondents' cognitive engagement and their academic performance. It was also found that the computed p -value of 0.000 is lesser than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) and the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the results provide strong evidence that student engagement in math was significantly associated with their academic performance.

Moreover, student engagement in mathematics plays a key role in the acquisition of math skills, and students who are engaged in the learning process tend to learn more to have a better performance in the subject. Furthermore, (Lei, Cui, & Zhou, 2018) stated that academic achievement is an important and consistent outcome of student engagement. So, a solid understanding of math concepts built through engagement equips students with a strong base for future learning in various aspects of life. Therefore, this cycle fosters a dynamic learning environment where the learners are actively involved, motivated, and ultimately successful in their math journey.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the respondents' statements were influenced by students' perceptions of cooperative learning in school, might not be directly impact to their grades but their attitudes of engagement were significantly relevant to their academic performance in mathematics that they experienced. In other words, students with positive perceptions of collaborative learning don't have automatically guaranteed high grades but it can lead to higher engagement in their math class and better performance. Therefore, by fostering positive perceptions of collaborative learning, schools can potentially increase student engagement and improve learning outcomes in mathematics.

Based on the findings and conclusion arrived in this study, it is recommended that the proposed mathematics performance enhancement plan would be adopted in order to enhance the students' engagement and performance in handling collaborative approaches in mathematics in the learning environment.

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